

SCREENING OF SALINITY TOLERANT RICE CULTIVARS

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Abstract

A preliminary screening experiment was conducted in the laboratory of Agronomy Department, Bangladesh Agricultural University (BAU), Mymensingh to find out the salinity tolerance of twenty rice varieties/landraces. Based on the germination performance under salinity stress, five most salt-tolerant cultivars/landraces were selected as: i) BINA dhan8 ii) Lal jamai babu iii) Super minicate iv) Hogla and v) Kajol lata. These five cultivars/landraces were used in a pot trial in the net house of the Department of Agronomy, BAU under seven levels of salinity viz., 0 mM, 20 mM, 40 mM, 60 mM, 80 mM, 100 mM and 120 mM NaCl during the *Boro* season of 2010-2011. The objective was to find out the salt tolerance levels of the cultivars/landraces. The results showed that yield and yield contributing characters viz., number of total tillers hill⁻¹, number of effective tillers hill⁻¹, grains panicle⁻¹, 1000-grain weight, grain yield hill⁻¹ and straw yield hill⁻¹ decreased gradually with the increased salinity levels. On the other hand, non-effective tillers hill⁻¹ and unfilled grains panicle⁻¹ increased with the increased level of salinity. Among these five varieties used Lal jamai babu could survive salinity level up to 120 mM followed by BINA dhan8 up to 100 mM NaCl, Kajol lata and Hogla up to 80 mM NaCl and Super minicate up to 60 mM NaCl. Based on their survival rate and yielding ability under various levels of salinity used in this study these varieties could be ranked as Lal jamai babu > BINA dhan8 > Hogla > Kajol lata > Super minicate.

Key words: rice; Landraces, Salinity tolerance, Screening.

Introduction

Presence of excess soluble salt is one of the major factors that reduces the growth and development of cultivated crop plant in coastal areas of the world. Nearly 20% of the world's cultivated area and about 50% of the world's irrigated lands are affected by salinity (Sairam and Tyagi, 2004). In Bangladesh, over 30% of the net cultivable area is in the coastal area (Karim *et al.*, 1990). Out of 2.85 million hectares of the coastal and offshore areas, about 0.83 million hectares are arable land, which constitute 52.8% of the net cultivable area in 64 Upazilla of 13 districts. More than 80 per cent of the total area of the districts Khulna, Bagerhat and Satkhira is already affected by different magnitudes of soil salinity of which about 35 per cent is in the grip of strong salinity (Mainuddin *et al.*, 2011). Agricultural land use in these areas is very minimum, which is much lower than the country's average cropping intensity (180%), ranging from 174% in the Chittagong coastal region to 137% in the Khulna coastal region (BBS, 2003). Rice is one of the major salt sensitive crop species (Mass and Haffman, 1977; Yeo and Flowers, 1982; Kader and Lindberg, 2005; Anil *et al.*, 2007; Kavitha *et al.*, 2012). Salinity level of 4 dSm⁻¹ is considered as critical level for rice. However, rice exhibits considerable intraspecific variability in resistance to salinity (Flowers and Yeo, 1981). Recently Bangladesh Institute of Nuclear Agriculture (BINA) has released a salinity tolerant rice cultivar namely BINA dhan8. There are some local varieties of rice endemic to the coastal

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region of many countries with a varying degree of salinity tolerance such as Pokkali, Nona bokra etc. In the coastal region of Bangladesh farmers have been cultivating many local salinity tolerant landraces of rice. Identification of salinity tolerant traits in these landraces of rice is very important for the plant breeders to develop high yielding salinity tolerant rice cultivars. Keeping above in mind the study was conducted to screen salinity tolerant landraces of rice endemic to the coastal area of Bangladesh and to determine the level of salinity tolerance of these landraces.

Materials and Methods

A preliminary germination test was conducted in the laboratory of the Department of Agronomy, Bangladesh Agricultural University (BAU), Mymensingh for screening of rice cultivars/landraces for salinity tolerance. Twenty varieties/landraces were included, such as Kajol lata, Hogla, BINA dhan8, Super minicate, Lal jamai babu, Nuncha aus, Sada jamai babu, Moynamoti, Doloe dhan, Urichadra, Koijuri, Raja morol, Sadajabra, Khasail, Ausfol, Morichshail, Sottorvog, Nijoli aus, Pokkali and Kalamona. Two levels of Salinity (mM), such as 0 mM NaCl (S_0) and 50 mM NaCl (S_1). Then all petridishes were placed in the laboratory followed by Completely Randomized Design (CRD) and one blotter paper was placed in each petridish. The commercial salt (NaCl) was used for developing salinity. For S_0 and S_1 treatments 0.00g and 38.06g of salts were added, respectively, in 1L water and dissolved. The solutions were then poured uniformly into the petridishes. Then the seeds (50) were placed in the petridishes and salinity levels of petridishes were monitored at 2 day intervals from the imposition of salinity up to the completion of the experiment. Finally, germination % was recorded. Then the growth performance experiment was conducted at the net house of the Department of Agronomy, Bangladesh Agricultural University (BAU), Mymensingh during the period from December 2010 to April 2011 to study the salinity tolerance level of five cultivars of rice selected from the preliminary screening trial. The soil was collected within 6 cm, from the top soil of the Agronomy Field Laboratory, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh. The soil covers a large area of the Brahmaputra River born sediments which was laid down before the river shifted into its Jamuna Channel about 200 years ago (UNDP and FAO, 1998). The experimental soil was loamy in texture having a soil pH value of 6.43, moderate in organic matter content. The experimental pots were filled up with soil (9 kg) and leveled. Puddled soils were fertilized according to the recommendation. In each pot full doses of chemical fertilizers viz. urea (1.7 g pot^{-1}), TSP (0.4 g pot^{-1}), MoP (0.71 g pot^{-1}), gypsum (0.25 g pot^{-1}), and zinc sulphate (0.035 g pot^{-1}) were applied. The total amount of TSP, MoP, gypsum and zinc sulphate (ZnSO_4) and one-third urea was applied during the final pot preparation and rest urea was top dressed at 20 and 40 days after transplanting (DAT). All the fertilizers were incorporated in the top most soil within 6 inch of the potted soil. One seedling of 40 days old was transplanted in the puddled soil of each pot in a hill. Five varieties were included in the experiment, such as Kajol lata, Hogla, BINA dhan8, Super minicate and Lal jamai babu. Seven levels of salinity (mM), such as 0 mM NaCl (S_0), 20 mM NaCl (S_1), 40 mM NaCl (S_2), 60 mM NaCl (S_3), 80 mM NaCl (S_4), 100 mM NaCl (S_5) and 120 mM NaCl (S_6) were imposed. The commercial salt (NaCl) was used for developing salinity. For S_0 , S_1 , S_2 , S_3 , S_4 , S_5 , and S_6 treatments 0.0g, 15.23g, 30.45g, 45.67g, 60.91g, 76.13g, and 91.35g of salts were added, respectively, in concerned pots. These amounts of salts were dissolved in 1000 ml of water and the solutions were then poured uniformly into the pots.

The saline treatments were given at 40 DAT. All intercultural operations were done as and when necessary. Crops were harvested at maturity stage. After harvesting data were collected on plant height (cm), no. of total tillers hill⁻¹, no. of effective tillers hill⁻¹, no. of non-effective tillers hill⁻¹, panicle length (cm), no. of grains panicle⁻¹, no. of sterile spikelets panicle⁻¹, 1000-grain weight (g), grain yield hill⁻¹ (g) and straw yield hill⁻¹ (g). The collected data were analyzed statistically following the analysis of variance (ANOVA) technique and the mean difference were adjudged by Duncan's Multiple Range Test (Gomez and Gomez, 1984) using the statistical computer package program MSTAT-C.

Results and Discussion

Effect of salinity level on germination of different rice cultivars

The effect of salinity level on germination of rice cultivars varied significantly at 1% level of significance (Table 1). The highest germination was found in BINA dhan8 (96.50 %) at control condition which was statistically similar to Kajol lata (91.00 %), Lal jamai babu (90.50 %), Pokkali (88.50 %) and Super minicate (88.00 %) at control condition. The lowest germination was found in Raja morol (57.00 %) at control condition. Under salinity stress condition (50 mM), the highest germination was also found in BINA dhan8 (92.50 %) and the lowest germination was found in Raja morol (41.50 %). The variety BINA dhan8 gave the highest germination both at control and salinity stressed conditions. Under salinity stress condition the lowest inhibition of germination was found in BINA dhan8 while the highest one in Kaijuri. Based on the germination performance under salinity stress, salt tolerant varieties were ranked as BINA dhan8> Lal jamai babu> Super minicate> Pokkali> Hogla> Kajol lata> Moynamoti> Nuncha aus> Kala mona> Khashail> Sada jamai babu> Urichadra> Doloe dhan> Sada jabra> Sottovog> Morichshail> Nijoli aus> Ausfol> Kaijuri> Raja morol.

From Table 2 it is seen that all plant characters of rice varied significantly due to salinity stress. Plant height was highest (91.08cm) at control and lowest (12.56cm) at the highest soil salinity of 120 mM. The results show that plant height decreased with the increasing salinity levels. The gradual decrease in plant height might be due to inhibition of cell division or cell enlargement for the salinity stress. The maximum number of tillers (15.67) was found at control condition and the minimum number (1.533) was obtained at 120 mM level of salinity. Number of tillers hill⁻¹ decreased with increasing salinity levels in comparison to that of the control. The highest number of effective tillers hill⁻¹ (14.60) was recorded in control. The lowest number of effective tillers hill⁻¹ (0.7333) was found in 120mM salinity stress. The number of effective tillers hill⁻¹ decreased probably due to less translocation of photosynthetic assimilates from the maximum tillering stage. The results also show that non-effective tillers hill⁻¹ increased from 40mM (1.80) to 60mM (2.287) salinity level. The highest panicle length (24.15cm) was found at control condition and the lowest (1.743 cm) was recorded at 120 mM level of soil salinity. Soil salinity might inhibit cell division or cell enlargement so that length of panicle was reduced. The highest number of grains panicle⁻¹ was recorded at control condition (74.40) and the lowest one (4.733) was recorded at 120mM level of soil salinity. The highest number of sterile spikelets panicle⁻¹ (12.60) was obtained at 80mM level of soil salinity and the lowest one (3.133) was recorded at 120mM level of soil salinity condition. The maximum weight (23.36g) of thousand grains was obtained from the control treatment which was

statistically similar to the salinity level of 20 mM (22.58g). The lowest 1000-grain weight (3.978g) was recorded in 120 mM level of soil salinity. The highest grain yield (23.23g hill⁻¹) was obtained in control treatment and the lowest (0.1173) was in 120 mM level of soil salinity. Reduced grains panicle⁻¹, 1000-grain weight and grain yield under salinity might be the results of lower assimilate production and lesser distribution towards reproductive part.

Table 1. Germination (%) performance of different *Boro* rice varieties in control and salinity condition

Variety	Control	Salt (50 mM salinity)	% germination inhibited due to salinity
Super Minicate	88.00abc	80.50b	8.52
Moynamoti	75.50cd	65.50def	13.25
Kajol lata	91.00ab	68.50cde	24.73
Raja morol	57.00e	41.50j	27.29
Hogla	79.50bcd	72.50bcd	8.81
Ausfol	70.00d	44.00ij	37.14
Kaijuri	70.50d	44.00ij	37.59
Sada jamai babu	76.50cd	59.50efg	22.22
Kala mona	81.50bcd	62.00efg	23.93
Doloe dhan	76.00cd	53.50ghi	29.61
BINA dhan8	96.50a	92.50a	4.15
Urichadra	74.50cd	55.50fgh	25.50
Khashail	74.50cd	60.00efg	19.46
Nuncha Aus	81.50bcd	65.00def	20.25
Lal jamai babu	90.50ab	81.00b	10.49
Sada jabra	75.50cd	53.50ghi	29.14
Morichshail	76.50cd	49.00hij	35.95
Sottovog	74.50cd	49.50hij	33.56
Nijoliaus	71.00d	46.00hij	35.21
Pokkali	88.50abc	76.00bc	14.12
Level of significance	**	**	-
CV%	10.75	10.06	-

In a column, figures with common letter(s) or without letter do not differ significantly whereas figures with dissimilar letters differ significantly (as per DMRT)

** = Significant at 1% level of probability.

From Table 3, the results show that the tallest plant produced by the variety Lal jamai babu (76.38 cm) followed by BINA dhan8 (66.33cm), Hogla (61.22cm), Kajol lata (53.69 cm) and the lowest value was produced by Super Minicate (42.04cm). The results show that different varieties had different degrees of salt tolerance capacity for plant height. The maximum number of tillers hill⁻¹ was found in Hogla (11.00) which was statistically similar to Lal jamai babu (10.52). The lowest tiller production was found in Super Minicate (4.476). The maximum number of effective tillers hill⁻¹ was counted in Hogla (9.476) and the minimum (6.333) was in Super Minicate, which indicates that the tolerance of different cultivars is different in producing effective tillers. The highest number of non-effective tillers hill⁻¹ was counted in Lal jamai babu (2.095) and the lowest number was counted in Super Minicate (1.110). The longest panicle of 18.99 cm was produced in BINA dhan8. The result was statistically identical to Hogla (12.22cm) and

Kajol lata (12.12cm). The shortest panicle of 10.28cm was produced in Super Minicate. The number of grains panicle⁻¹ was highest (61.57) in BINA dhan8 and the lowest number of grains panicle⁻¹ was observed in Super Minicate (27.95). The highest number of sterile spikelets panicle⁻¹ (10.10) was found in Lal jamai babu and the lowest number (6.190) was attained in Super Minicate. The highest thousand grain weight (21.46g) was noticed in Lal jamai babu and the lowest (10.33g) weight of thousand grains was recorded in Super Minicate. The best grain yield performance was found in BINA dhan8 (11.81g hill⁻¹) which was statistically similar to Hogla (11.19g hill⁻¹) and the lowest yield was recorded 4.903g hill⁻¹ in Super Minicate rice variety.

Table 2. Effect of salinity stress on plant characters and yield of *Boro* rice

Salinity level (mM)	Plant height (cm)	Total tillers hill ⁻¹	Effective tillers hill ⁻¹	Non-effective tillers hill ⁻¹	Panicle length (cm)	Grains panicle ⁻¹	Sterile spikelets panicle ⁻¹	1000 grain weight (g)	Grain yield hill ⁻¹ (g)
0	91.08a	15.67a	14.60a	1.067e	24.15a	74.40a	5.533e	23.36a	23.23a
20	84.49b	14.07b	12.73b	1.333d	21.37b	69.00b	7.400c	22.58ab	17.60b
40	78.06c	12.73c	10.87c	1.800c	18.25c	58.87c	9.133b	21.69bc	11.79c
60	71.49d	11.47d	9.200d	2.287a	15.24d	47.27d	12.53a	20.96c	6.867d
80	54.37e	7.933e	5.933e	2.000b	11.40e	32.80e	12.60a	17.12d	3.148e
100	27.48f	3.200f	2.133f	1.067e	5.743f	14.93f	6.333d	8.685e	0.9867f
120	12.56g	1.533g	0.7333g	0.8000f	1.743g	4.733g	3.133f	3.978f	0.1173f
Level of significance	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**
CV (%)	9.50	11.19	13.29	15.50	15.84	7.55	9.53	12.20	13.55

Table 3. Effect of variety on plant characters and yield of *Boro* rice

Variety	Plant height (cm)	Total tillers hill ⁻¹ (no.)	Effective tillers hill ⁻¹ (no.)	Non-effective tillers hill ⁻¹ (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Sterile spikelets panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	1000 grain weight (g)	Grain yield hill ⁻¹ (g)
Kajol lata	53.69d	10.00b	8.667b	1.333c	12.12c	35.10c	7.714c	14.69c	7.883c
Hogla	61.22c	11.00a	9.476a	1.524b	12.22c	36.71c	7.333c	17.65b	11.19a
Super minicate	42.04e	7.476d	6.333d	1.110d	10.28d	27.95d	6.190d	10.33d	4.903d
Lal jamai babu	76.38a	10.52ab	8.429b	2.095a	16.32b	54.38b	10.10a	21.46a	9.745b
BINA dhan8	66.33b	8.571c	7.238c	1.333c	18.99a	61.57a	9.143b	20.42a	11.81a
Level of significance	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**
CV (%)	9.50	11.19	13.29	15.50	15.84	7.55	9.53	12.20	13.55

In a column, figures with common letter or without letter do not differ significantly whereas figures with dissimilar letters differ significantly (as per DMRT).

** indicates significant at 1% level of probability.

As evidenced from Table 4, the adverse effects of salinity stress on plant characters of rice differed in different varieties of rice. The tallest plant of 106.9 cm was produced from Hogla variety at control condition. The shortest plant (60.23cm) was found in the variety Hogla at 80 mM. However, when salinity level increased to 120mM only Lal jamai babu could survive with plant height of 62.78 cm and other varieties did not survive. Number of total tillers hill⁻¹ was highest (19.33) in Hogla at control condition and the lowest number (7.333) was recorded from BINA dhan8 at 100 mM salinity level. Maximum number (18.33) of effective tillers hill⁻¹ was observed at control condition in

Hogla. In Lal jamai babu, at 120 mM salinity levels effective tillers hill⁻¹ was 3.667 but other varieties in that salinity level did not survive. The maximum number (4.000) of non-effective tillers hill⁻¹ was counted in Lal jamai babu under 120 mM and the lowest number (0.6667) of non-effective tillers hill⁻¹ was found in BINA dhan8 in comparison to other varieties at the same level of salinity. The highest panicle length (28.09cm) was observed in BINA dhan8 at control condition, but at 120 mM total hill died of all varieties except Lal jamai babu. The highest number of grains panicle⁻¹ (93.33) was produced in BINA dhan8 at control condition. The lowest grains panicle⁻¹ (23.67) was recorded in Super minicate at 60 mM. The magnitude of reduction of grains panicle⁻¹ in the varieties with the salinity levels were Lal jamai babu > Super minicate > Kajol lata > Hogla > BINA dhan8. The lowest number of filled grains (8.000) were found in Lal jamai babu at 120 mM of soil salinity level but other varieties did not survive at this salinity level. The highest 1000-grain weight (26.62g) was found in Hogla at control condition and the lowest weight was found in Super minicate at 60 mM (16.47g). The highest grain yield hill⁻¹ (29.78g) was found in Hogla at control condition. The lowest grain yield hill⁻¹ (0.5867g) was found in Lal jamai babu at 120 mM level of soil salinity. At higher level of soil salinity (120 mM) only Lal jamai babu gave the grain yield but other varieties did not survive under study. It can be concluded that plant height, number of total tillers hill⁻¹, number of effective tillers hill⁻¹, panicle length, number of grains panicle⁻¹, thousand grain weight and grain yield hill⁻¹ decreased gradually with increased salinity levels. But number of non-effective tillers hill⁻¹, number of unfilled grains panicle⁻¹ increased with the increased level of salinity.

Table 4. Interaction of variety and salinity level on plant characters and yield of Boro rice

Variety	Salinity level (mM)	Plant height (cm)	Total tillers hill ⁻¹ (No.)	Effective tillers hill ⁻¹ (No.)	Non-effective tillers hill ⁻¹ (No.)	Panicle length (cm)	Grains panicle ⁻¹ (No.)	Sterile spikelets panicle ⁻¹ (No.)	1000 grain weight (g)	Grain yield hill ⁻¹ (g)
Kajol lata	0	83.67c-g	17.33b	16.33b	1.000hi	23.1bc	64.67ef	3.667m	22.53b-i	22.12cd
	20	79.00e-i	15.67bc	14.00c	1.667fg	19.75b-f	58.00gh	7.333jk	21.43c-j	15.20f
	40	74.00g-k	14.33cde	12.33c-f	2.000ef	16.05f-i	52.00i	9.333i	20.69d-j	10.90g
	60	71.33h-m	12.33e-i	10.00h-k	2.333de	13.93h-k	42.67j	14.33cd	19.67g-k	5.603kl
	80	67.83j-n	10.33ijk	8.00l-p	2.333de	11.97jkl	28.33kl	19.33a	18.50ijk	1.360mn
	100	0.0000 o	0.0000n	0.0000r	0.0000j	0.0000m	0.0000m	0.0000n	0.0000l	0.0000n
	120	0.0000 o	0.0000n	0.0000r	0.0000j	0.000m	0.000m	0.000n	0.000l	0.0000n
Hogla	0	106.9a	19.33a	18.33a	1.000hi	23.00bc	66.33de	5.333l	26.62a	29.78a
	20	96.62b	17.33b	16.33b	1.000hi	21.33b-e	63.67efg	6.333kl	25.53ab	23.90c
	40	90.26bcd	15.33cd	12.67c-e	2.667cd	18.15d-g	57.00hi	8.667ij	24.43a-e	14.94f
	60	74.57g-k	13.67def	11.33e-h	2.333de	12.67i-l	42.33j	12.67ef	23.96a-f	8.057ij
	80	60.23n	11.33g-j	7.667m-p	3.667a	10.42kl	27.67kl	18.33a	23.05a-g	1.647mn
	100	0.0000o	0.0000n	0.0000r	0.0000j	0.0000m	0.0000m	0.0000n	0.0000l	0.000n
	120	0.0000o	0.0000n	0.0000r	0.0000j	0.000m	0.0000m	0.0000n	0.0000l	0.0000n
Super minicate	0	86.19c-f	15.33cd	13.67cd	1.667fg	23.46b	66.33de	7.667jk	19.50g-k	15.63ef
	20	79.28e-h	13.33efg	12.00d-g	1.333gh	21.05b-e	60.00fgh	9.333hi	18.87h-k	11.27g
	40	68.00i-n	12.33f-i	10.33g-j	1.667fg	16.10f-i	45.67j	11.00g	17.47jk	6.257kl
	60	60.80mn	11.33hij	8.333k-o	3.100b	11.35jkl	23.67l	15.33bc	16.47k	1.153mn
	80	0.0000o	0.0000 n	0.0000r	0.0000j	0.0000m	0.000m	0.0000n	0.0000l	0.0000n
	100	0.0000o	0.0000 n	0.0000r	0.0000j	0.0000m	0.0000m	0.0000n	0.0000l	0.0000n
	120	0.0000o	0.0000 n	0.0000r	0.0000j	0.0000m	0.0000m	0.0000n	0.0000l	0.0000n

Table 4. Continued

Variety	Salinity level (mM)	Plant height (cm)	Total tillers hill ⁻¹ (No.)	Effective tillers hill ⁻¹ (No.)	Non-effective tillers hill ⁻¹ (No.)	Panicle length (cm)	Grains panicle ⁻¹ (No.)	Sterile spikelets panicle ⁻¹ (No.)	1000 grain weight (g)	Grain yield hill ⁻¹ (g)
Lal jamai babu	0	93.10bc	13.67def	12.67cde	1.000hi	23.10bc	81.33bc	5.333l	23.03a-g	22.17cd
	20	86.44cde	12.33f-i	10.67f-i	1.667fg	20.75b-e	79.67bc	6.667kl	22.30b-i	17.48e
	40	80.19d-h	11.33g-j	9.667h-l	1.667fg	19.12c-f	63.33efg	8.333ij	21.91b-i	11.66g
	60	75.32f-k	10.33jik	8.667j-n	1.667fg	17.12e-h	56.67hi	9.667hi	21.47b-i	8.757hi
	80	70.30h-n	9.667kl	7.333nop	2.333de	14.78g-j	44.67j	11.67fg	21.05d-j	5.103l
	100	66.52k-n	8.667klm	6.333p	2.333de	10.65kl	31.33k	13.33de	20.56e-j	2.463m
BINA dhan8	0	85.55c-f	12.67e-h	12.00d-g	0.6667i	28.09a	93.33a	5.667l	25.13abc	26.44b
	20	81.14d-h	11.67f-j	10.67e-i	1.000hi	23.95b	83.67b	7.333jk	24.76a-d	20.15d
	40	77.83e-j	10.33jik	9.333i-m	1.000hi	21.84bcd	76.33c	8.333ij	23.94a-f	15.18f
	60	75.43f-k	9.667kl	7.667m-p	2.000ef	21.11b-e	71.00d	10.67gh	23.26a-g	10.76gh
	80	73.48g-l	8.333lm	6.667op	1.667fg	19.85b-f	63.33efg	13.67de	23.00a-g	7.630ijk
	100	70.87h-n	7.333m	4.333q	3.000bc	18.07d-g	43.33j	18.33a	22.86a-h	2.470m
	120	0.0000o	0.0000n	0.0000r	0.0000j	0.0000m	0.0000m	0.0000n	0.0000l	0.0000n
Level of significance	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**
CV (%)		9.50	11.19	13.29	15.50	15.84	7.55	9.53	12.20	13.55

In a column, figures with common letter or without letter do not differ significantly whereas figures with dissimilar letters differ significantly (as per DMRT).

** Indicates 1% level of probability

From the experimental results it could be concluded that BINA dhan8 was more salt tolerant than other varieties/landraces on the basis of germination performance. On the other hand, concerning growth and yield performance Lal jamai babu was appeared as the most salt tolerant variety which was followed by BINA dhan8. The experimental results also show that Super minicate was more susceptible to increasing salinity levels. Therefore, from adaptability point of view; the experiment may be repeated at different locations with varying levels of soil salinity and climatic conditions of the country for arriving at a final recommendation.

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